

Negotiating Contested Reality: A study of Presidency College Archives

Abstract: This paper attempts to map the ways in which student subjectivities of Hindoo College were shaped, regulated and negotiated in colonized India between 1914 - 1947 through the analysis of Presidency College Magazines archived by Dr. Upal Chakraborty in association with British Library. This paper attempts to map archival discontinuities and thematic shifts. It attempts to situate the content of the magazine as a discursive site where colonial power, nationalist aspiration and intellectual inquiry intersect. Drawing on Foucault's conception of discourse and Althusser's notion of interpellation, this essay highlights how student voices operated within colonial educational institution. This essay foregrounds the discontinuities and silences within the archive narrating unstable assemblage of hegemonized subjects shaped by shifting political currents. This paper situates Presidency College Magazine as an archive of contested voices and highlights the debates on entanglement of knowledge, power and political imagination in colonial India.

Keywords: *Colonialism, Bengal, Archival research, subjectivity, discourse, educational institution*

Introduction

The long 19th and 20th Century altered the course of Indian History. This phase was marked by the perpetual subjugation of the Indian masses, but it also paved way to the rise of political consciousness, resulting in the nationalist struggle. The Nationalist Movement can be divided into three phases – The Early Nationalist Phase (1885-1905) The Assertive Phase (1905-1918) The Gandhian Phase (1919-1947). Education served as one of the important pillars, leading to the emergence Indian Political Consciousness. Calcutta (now Kolkata) was the capital of the British empire in India (prior to 1911). It was in Calcutta, that the first western educational institution was established (Fort William College 1800 estd.), attempting to manufacture a clerical class in the colony. Soon other institutions were also established, celebrated among them was the Hindu College, founded on 20th January 1817 at a rented house in Garanhatta¹. The Hindu College was divided into two sections – a Pathshala (school)² and a Mahapathshala³. After the liquidation of Baretto and Sons⁵ (1923), the members of the governing body applied for financial support to the government. With time the institution went under government control and finally in 1855, abandoning the Hindu exclusivism, the Hindu College was converted into Presidency college, opening its gates to all sections of the society. The college shifted to its present campus on 31 March 1874 with the initiative of its distinguished principal J Sutcliffe. This progress led to a change of teaching staff (maximum teachers were British), course structure (The college was divided on the basis of year and course) and fees structure (there was a fees hike from Rs-5 to Rs 12). But the popularity of the institution attracted students from everywhere.^{6 7} It is very interesting to note that, 19th and 20th century was also a witness to socio-political transformation, marked by the two great wars of all times. Literature is an imperative to reconstruct the history of a given period, but devoid of its socio-political backdrop it is incomplete. In this sessional I will thus try to study the socio-political reality with reference to selected writings from the Presidency College Magazine.

¹ 175th Anniversary Commemoration Vol. 2, P. 1

² imparting instruction in English, Bengali, Arithmetic and Grammar

³ where History, Geography, Chronology, Astronomy, Mathematics, Chemistry and other sciences were taught in English Bengali and Persian

⁴ 175th Anniversary Commemoration Vol. 2, P. 2

⁵ Initial Sponsor

⁶ 175th Anniversary Commemoration Volume 1992

⁷ Knowledge Power and Politics, edited by Mushirul Hasan, p.304-325

I intend to inspect the timeline from 1914-1947 keeping in mind the temporality of unrest. My sessional will try to navigate through the essays, from the college magazine, comparing and contrasting the comprehensive socio-political occurrences of Bengal and India. The themes covered by the magazine portrays a picture of the institution and its students. My essential purpose would be to tap into the voices of the students (of the above-mentioned timeline) within the campus and locating the underlined political consciousness, through their essays. The first section of this paper will try to recognize the regulatory parameters and locate the voice of the amidst the scrutiny. The second section will deal with the discontinuities in reconstruction of history from archival documents, problematizing my entire attempt in a generalized manner.

1. Voices Unheard

The Presidency College magazine was first issued on November 1914 by Henry Rosher James, the then principal of the institution. From 1914 onwards 6 magazines were published in a year (although there were times when 6 issues could not be published or are not available in the achieve) whose first editor was Pramatha Nath Banerjee and Assistant Editor was Mr. Joges Chandra Chakravarti. As H. R James wrote in the introductory section of the first published magazine *“A college magazine is an organ of the corporate life of the college.... it should Chronicle events; it should communicate views; it should afford opportunities for the free discussion of College affairs and interests.... it will give us information valuable to us in our ordinary life:- notice of events which concern the college as a whole or sections of it; the Constitution of clubs, seminars, societies; accounts of meetings; changes in the routine of studies; information concerning scholarships and prices; reports of matches; social news of all sorts; university news and general educational news. News must of course be kept within limits, and the limits are given precisely enough by bearing on the interests of college life.”*⁸

1914 was a crucial year in the history of mankind. It marks the beginning of the First World War which affected the nations and its colonies alike. Presidency College played its part during the crisis of the empire. All members of the college, teachers, students and staff made contribution to the ‘Relief Fund’ set up for the aid of the crisis. It is well known that the Indian Troops were dispatched to Europe during the war. The life of the people in the colonies was equally affected, illustrated in the opening sections of the first issue of the magazine.⁹ It can be said that the socio-political events had its impact even on the campus life of students. Social Reformers, Lawyers, Professors, Freedom Fighters, Scientists and many other great minds of Bengal were products of Presidency College. Hence it cannot be denied that the political consciousness was already present within the campus. What needs to be located is how and to what extent this socio-political consciousness was expressed in the through the magazines. To do so, I have divided the archive in 3 sections – 1914-1919 ; 1920-1929 ; 1930-1947, based on the thematic transformation. The magazines illumines a transition elaborated in the succeeding sections.

1.1. 1914-1919

The chronological political mayham altered the European as well as in Indian social order.ⁱ 18 magazines had been published in the course of 5 academic years. Uncovering the voice through literary

⁸ Presidency College Magazine 1914, p.2

⁹ Presidency College Magazine 1914, p.4

documents is a arduous project, but not an impossible one. But a crucial question remains. Whose voice are we trying to locate? The voice of hegemonized European subjects in the making Or the voice deep embedded within the cultural subject? Is it possible for a subject to have a voice at all, given the long years of hegemonizing process through education? All these questions are contextual. As Bernard Cohn rightly said, “The conquest of India was a conquest of knowledge.”¹⁰ The college life, similar to that of publication was kept ‘in limits’; the limits decided by the authority.

The topics published in these years of uncertainty highlighted the docile subjects of the colony. The phase of assertive nationalist struggle failed to make it to the pages of the documents. The columnists indulged into comprehensive philosophical questions. But what about nation? Did the students fail to imagine a free nation? I would argue otherwise but is important to also note that their expression was constitutional or rather constitutional columns were published exclusively. For instance, The story of Bharatmata¹¹. It illustrated how the two ladies (Bharatmata and Britania) like sisters supported each other. This liaison called for India’s assistance during the war “*not as subjects of a dependency of the British Empire, but as loyal-hearted, free-hearted citizens and comrades.*”¹² As loyal citizens, congress swore allegiance and million ‘sons of Bhatarmata’ set out to defend ‘Lady Britania’.

It is very interesting to note multiple narratives a said time period according to subjective locations. What then is the reality? Was it the one reflected through the columns of the magazines or was it that, which was happening outside the college campus? I would argue, reality was much more than that¹³. The scrutiny and censorship over the college magazine made it impossible for the nonconformists to reach to the it pages. And the ‘tyranny’¹⁴ of the editor vis-à-vis authority was evident in this context. This monopoly of the Editor was lambasted vehemently through the correspondence, entailing the authoritative hold to be outrageous and infringement to students rights.¹⁵ Here it is crucial to mention that, the college magazine was also used by the authority to communicate with the students at large. The principal H.R James through his essay Responsibility and Irresponsibility, addressed the student, sternly delineating the postulates of responsibility embedded in “*mutual relation...universal law of consideration and courtesy*”¹⁶ between the Indians and the Europeans within the campus. This essay similarly emphasizes the unyielding disparity between Indian and their western counterparts, which frequently suspension the smooth functioning of the college. This disruption was not released in the form of news. As a matter of fact, none of the events which disrupted the smooth functioning of the college life made its way to the pages of the magazine. But then the question arises what kind of news were published? The news mainly consisted of events devoid of a political undertone, like the achievements of the alumni, the rules and regulation about examination, the then current updates about war, and so on. 1914-19 was also marked by the famine in India, as a response to which, Presidency College established a relief fund to support the people affected, and updates on the allocation of the fund can be spotted in each edition of Volume 2. This indicates the students participation in national crisis advocating for their conscious approach towards extending assistance in a critical situation. It

¹⁰ Colonialism and its Forms of Knowledge, Bernard S. Cohn, Princeton University Press, P. 16

¹¹ Presidency College Magazine 1915, Vol-1. No.3, The Story of Bharatmata, G.S Dutt, P.205

¹² Presidency College Magazine 1914, Vol-1, No.1, Principal’s Address, *Presidency College, Aug. 25, 1914*, P.32

¹³ I will attempt to answer this question in the conclusion

¹⁴ Presidency College Magazine 1915, Vol-1, No.3 My First Year in Presidency College, Probhas Chandra Ghosh, P.238

¹⁵ Presidency College Magazine 1915, Vol-1, No.3 My First Year in Presidency College, Probhas Chandra Ghosh, P. 294

¹⁶ Presidency College Magazine 1916, Vol-2, No.5, Responsibility and Irresponsibility, H.R. James, P.309

can thus be assumed that the non-conformist and rebellious population of the college were prevented off their faculty to influence larger sections of the college. Often laws and regulations were aimed controlling the non-conformist masses, for instance the Prevention of Seditious Meetings Act (1911) ordered the chaos near the common room supressing “the talks about sedition”¹⁷ post 1911.

Student life in Presidency was not only about providing the authority with ‘civil servants’¹⁸ it was also about protesting against the despotism of the Sahibs. *“As for the students, I really do not know what has come over them. In my youth I always found them gay, lively and impulsive, even violent, much more loud in their talk,. much more ready to look you straight in the face if you wronged them, or if they fancied they had been wronged. I remember their passion for fighting; on one occasion their fight was with the Sahib students of the Medical College, and so bitter was the feeling roused that, for eight full days it continued, and the students of all the Colleges practically blocked the streets between Kalitola and Bowbazar. The matter went to the Court even, and when one of the arrested Babus was ordered to remain in the lock-up till his trial, a huge crowd gathered around him and his guard, and declared they were not going to allow that. But he bowed to his friends in recognition of their sympathy, smiled, and said that, as he thought he was guilty, he had better go. The case, however, was decided in favour of the Indian students.”*¹⁹ The times were changing, within and outside the college recalls the senior college bearer, *“ One could feel then that there were men in the College; for whenever the students found an empty room, they assembled there in great numbers, sang and recited poetry pieces, regardless of the remonstrances of the Professors that might be engaged in work close by. It continued as late as the days of Percival Sahib; but in his time as soon as the news that he had come to College got spread, all was silent.”*²⁰ History has been a witness to age old traditions of power play. And it is history which recorded and celebrated the administration of an empire. Manuscripts of prescribed conduct can be traced back to the Vedic ages. Hence the valorisation of judiciary in each historical epoch had been tremendous, maybe because the historians were a tool of governance. Each era embarked on the historical records produced by court historians where the sovereign recreated the reality, an elite reality. This epoch was no different. Thus The Lucknow Pact, Home rule Movement, Champaran Satyagraha, The Jallianwala Bagh Massacre was censored.

1.2. 1920-1929

The phase was marked by an overall thematic shift in the magazine. News concerning the nationalist movement popped up from time to time in the editor’s column. In the broader socio-political realm of Indiaⁱⁱ, this period entailed crucial changes under the leadership of Gandhi. 1920 onwards articles engaging with Economical aspects of India were indulged. Moreover, the principals address in the ‘forward’ was amenable, compared to previous volumes. 1920’s witnessed the birth of active students’ participation in Indian Politics. The first sporadic student protest can be traced back to 1905 when the boarders of Hindu hostel burned the effigy of Lord Curzon and British Clothes. They resolved to boycott the examination in response to the British policy of divide and rule. The movement spearheaded by Bipin Chandra Pal and Surendra Nath Banerji, was the steppingstone of the student’s movement in India. it was only after 1920 that there was an upsurge of youth membership in congress who spontaneously invested themselves in the project of Nation Building. This change was witnessed

¹⁷ Presidency College Magazine 1915, Vol-1, No.3, Presidency College in 1910

¹⁸ Presidency College Magazine 1917, Vol-3, No. 3, A message from one at a long distance in time, Gooroo Das Banerjee, P. 152

¹⁹ Presidency College Magazine 1917, Vol-4, No. 1, A Evening Talk about the College History with the Senior College Bearer, Phanibhusan Chakravarti, P. 47

²⁰ Presidency College Magazine 1917, Vol-4, No. 1, A Evening Talk about the College History with the Senior College Bearer, Phanibhusan Chakravarti, P. 47

in the magazines as well, where students began to raise the issues and resolutions taken up by the INC. Other youth organizations were also formed.

Strong voices within the magazine addressed the idea of a governmentality, it pointed out the defects of Dyarchy²¹, it upheld a picture of village (with a Marxist undertone)²², it talked about the life of women and how that ought to change²³, It also pointed out the problems faced by common people due to the continuous political turmoil²⁴. Contrarily there were essays mentioning about India's Incapability to obtain Purna Swaraj because India had to depend on the British for defense²⁵. Rapid transformation of the political scenario was reflected on the college magazine. The students expressed their thoughts on the imagination of a free nation. Highlighting facts about the economic problems of the country, they urged the Indian representatives in the government to rethink the drudgery suffered by the people due to Permanent Settlement. *"In view of the serious economic situation in Bengal it is necessary that the members of the Local Council and the Province as a whole should explore the possibilities of raising money for better administration of the ' Nation-building ' departments in a direction which is not likely to affect the people keenly.* ²⁶" *"A rapid development of industries will free the land of our birth from economic bondage to the West and will,—I am led to hope—be her salvation.*"²⁷ Some of them also shared radical ideas about 'Birth Taxation'²⁸ as a measure to eradicate the problem of overpopulation, whereas others enlightened their readers with subjective insights on the fallacy of the spinning wheel²⁹ (this topic was taken up in response to the non-cooperation movement (1920), where Gandhi urged the Indians to take up charkha, a symbol of self-sufficiency and freedom.) It is very interesting to note that the fallacy of the charkha was pointed out by a BA student of Presidency College much before the Great Depression of 1930 that influenced Nehru to rethink about the economic conditions of the country³⁰. The literate youth were involved in re-imagining the education system. Post-1928,^{31,32} they demanded modification of examination from Calcutta University. Gandhi's call to boycott every government college and take up charkha was taken seriously by the students, resulting in less submission for the magazines³³ and suspension of classes³⁴.

At this juncture it can be argued that the rapid transformation in the socio-political scenario helped the students of Presidency college to express their views on the then present condition of the society. It is not that the authorities' control on the magazine was lifted but rather it was forced to liberalize due to the active teacher-student participation in the nationalist struggle. The time of a certain historical period has an effect on the people living through it, but the expression of their views is regulated by the men in control. The magazine is the witness to the transformation outside campus.

²¹ Presidency College Magazine 1921, Vol-8, No. 1, The Defects of Dyarchy, Nirmal Chandra Chatterjee, P.20

²² Presidency College Magazine 1921, Vol-8, No. 1, The Bengali Village, Pramatha Nath Chakravarti, P. 60

²³ Presidency College Magazine 1921, Vol-8, No. 2, Bengali Bride in her new Home, Bimal Kumar Bhattacharya, P. 93

²⁴ Presidency College Magazine 1921, Vol-8, No. 3, Agriculture in Noakhali, M Abdur Rouf, P. 63

²⁵ Presidency College Magazine 1921, Vol-8, No. 2, Thoughts on Swaraj, R.N. Gilchrist, P.99

²⁶ Presidency College Magazine 1922, Vol-8, No. 3, Thoughts on the Permanent Settlement and Bengals Finance, Dharendra Nath Sen, P.45

²⁷ Presidency College Magazine 1922, Vol-9, No. 3, The Industrial Possibilities of India, Devaprasanna Mukherji, P.286

²⁸ Presidency College Magazine 1923, Vol-10, No. 1, Birth Taxation, Pavitra Kumar Basu, P.20

²⁹ Presidency College Magazine 1926, Vol-13, No. 1, The Economic Fallacy of the Spinning Wheel. Sushil Kumar Dey, 17

³⁰ The Hindu, May 29, 1964

³¹ Presidency College Magazine 1923, Vol-10, No. 1, The Ideal of University Education, Subodh Kumar Dutt, P.64

³² Presidency College Magazine 1926, Vol-12, No. 3, Primary Education In Bengal, P. Prof. D Chatteraj, P.214

³³ Presidency College Magazine 1929, Vol-15, No. 2, Editorial Notes

³⁴ Presidency College Magazine 1928, Vol-14, No. 3, Editorial Notes

1.3. 1930-1947

“The student militancy on Bengal continued to increase in early 1930’s... Demonstration of students shouting revolutionary and nationalist slogans were very popular and several attempts were made by students to assassinate high Government officials”³⁵

Various documents are found in Presidency University archive which indicated the unrest within the campus. The Civil disobedience movement launched by Gandhi influenced the students to take up actions against the authority giving rise to a number of strikes and violent protests within the campus³⁶. Several pamphlets had been confiscated and *“The British Government suspected that the students of Presidency College might be secretly associated with revolutionary activities and they might also use chemicals, stored in the laboratory, to make bombs.”³⁷* They started picketing colleges in the 1930’s which included Presidency College, Bethune College and Scottish Church College, stretching throughout the month of July.³⁸ By 1932, as the movement reached its peak, most of the organizations were banned forcing them to go underground.³⁹

Given the chaos within the campus, the domain to the magazine was rather quiet. In this span of 17 years only 11 volumes of magazines could be published. In 1942 a Government Circular was released, banning the publication of school and college magazine. Hence, post-1942 one magazine was published on January 1947 consisting of miscellaneous articles and reports. 1930ⁱⁱⁱ onwards an interesting development took place in the series of the college magazines. The political news about congress’s resolutions and interaction with the British government started to get published in the ‘Notes and News’ sections along with multiple articles concerning the socio-economic scenario of the country. Some corroborated to the congress policies while others challenged it, but nonetheless, there was an unanimous support for the nationalist movement, through diverse interpretation of an array of social questions. In fact, the editorial column had a pro-congress undertone.⁴⁰ Finally, from this period onwards, it can be said that the socio-political alterations echoed through the pages of the magazine. The imagination of the ‘Nation’ undermined the British representation of the college life. The space within the college, merged with the larger social order. The hold of the authority over the students were reduced. Anti-colonialist struggle finally succeeded in 1947, but could the Indians free themselves off the colonization of the mind? That’s a question which I will try to address in the next section.

Conclusion

In this paper I have attempted to elaborate on the subjectivity of the students of Presidency College. Subjectivity is a slippery zone. A subject is a seat of discursive subjectivities. One’s action in a particular situation illustrates one subjective position in the society.⁴¹ In attempting to do so I have definitely outlined my own subjective position. Being a present student of Presidency University and

³⁵ Political Consciousness among college students, A.B. Shinde, sodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in

³⁶ Letters 1930.

³⁷ artsandculture.google.com

³⁸ Political Consciousness among college students, A.B. Shinde, sodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in

³⁹ Political Consciousness among college students, A.B. Shinde, sodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in

⁴⁰ Presidency College Magazine 1933-1939, Notes and News

⁴¹ The Archaeology of Knowledge, Michel Foucault, Vintage

the writer of this paper, I may have illustrated my biases (although I tried avoiding it). Since it is true for all historical epochs the question arises about the discourse on writing (which is not within the scope of this sessional).

The articles in the magazine represents a dialectical subjectivity. The experience within and outside campus was heavily regularized. It is a known fact that, the people's life was already divided into the spaces between 'inside' and 'outside'⁴². In fact, their time too was fragmented⁴³, where the office time and the life outside, governed their existence. English education further problematized the situation. The students, as I had mentioned earlier, were important actors in the project of nation building. But was the imagination of the nation purely native? Could the perpetrators be able to imagine a nation without the influence of the foreign ideals if they were educated in English? The Bengali literature that was developed during the 19th and 20th century too had traces of English literature. The position of writers as well as politicians were marked by the dialectics of that time. Therefore, in this paper I attempted to inspect the regularities. The subject is discontinuous and always-already fragmented between its multiple subjectivities. The dialectics of subject-position makes the reconstruction of temporal historicity (without biases) problematic.

The transformation in publication pattern in 1920's and 30's is an example of a relocation of subjective position/experience. And the surveillance on the magazine illustrates the dialectics of a temporal-subject. In is very interesting to note the fragmented campus space. Caught up between the rules and regulation, the student's life illustrated discontinuity between the conformists and nonconformists. This was no different from the what was happening outside the gates of 86/1 College Street. The response to this situation was a negotiation between violent protest and constitutional approach. It is no different from the present scenario in Presidency university where few students go for hunger strike and others take up the procedure of deputation and requests. It is the universal dialectics between the authority and the subjects, be it foreign or native. As is well said by Althusser, "*All ideology hails or interpellates concrete individuals as concrete subjects, through the functioning of the category of the subject*"⁴⁴

Thus, to answer to the question about voice, raised in the initial section, I would like to point out that, it is the voice of both the cultural and hegemonized European subject I attempted to trace through the magazine. Since a historical period is a result of braided subjectivity, the epoch cannot be studied by championing one voice whereas silencing the rest. The method of re-construction is a discursive process, failing to realize which, will lead to misinterpretation. It is also true that, not all aspects could be addressed through this paper which obviously represents a discontinuity, not in the student's consciousness of that time, but in the expression of it. The student's consciousness is not well documented within the achieves, the available documents and are subjected to interpretation. On the other hand, the phase is marked by the manipulation of written documents. This paper is also restricted in its own field given the unavailability of the articles which were rejected for publication. This discontinuity will keep affecting similar attempts as mine. Thus, I would conclude by stating that, *Reality of the time* was the combination of multiple subjectivities within and outside campus, it was a combination of the expressed and unexpressed. *Reality* is the combination of thought that was acted upon and thought that was deferred.

⁴² Writing Social History, Sumit Sarkar, Oxford University Press

⁴³ Small Voices of History, Part 3, The Two Histories of Empire, Ranajit Guha, Permanent Black

⁴⁴ On the Reproduction of Capitalism, Louis Althusser, Verso, P. 190

ⁱ 1914: - Beginning of World War I

- Troops were sent from India on August to fight against Germany.
- On October they participated in the Battle of Ypres.
- Bengal Ambulance Corps (BAC) was set up on the money borne by the people of Bengal, to send paramedics to war front.
- BAC was sent to Mesopotamia where they assisted war-hit soldiers. They served till 1916
- Two meetings were held on 12th August and 8th September in Hostel and Physics lab with the members of Young Bengal where they promised to extend help for the war
- Professors agreed to make monthly contribution from their salary at a fixed rate till the war lasts. The office and library staff did the same.
- Contributions were divided into 3 sections based on donation – 1 paisa, 2 paisa and 3 paisa respectively

1915: - Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi Returned to India

- Introduction of Famine relief fund in Presidency College

1916: - The Lucknow Pact

- Home rule Movement
- Creation of the Bengalee Regiment

1917: - Indian National Congress demanded self-governance

- Gandhi Started Champaran Satyagraha
- Bengalee Regiment was formed

1918: - The Great Bengal Famine

- End of First World War

1919: - The Jalianwallabagh Massacre

- Gandhi declared all India Strike against Rowlett Act
- The Government of India Act was enacted

ⁱⁱ 1920: - Non-cooperation Movement

- All India college students conference was held at Nagpur, under the presidentship of Lala Lajpat Rai. The resolution on. The non-cooperation and the boycott of schools and colleges was passed.

1921: - Parliamentary Advisory Counsel of Princes was inaugurated

- Counsel of state and legislative assembly was inaugurated
- King Edward VIII arrived in India and was greeted with agitation in Bombay.
- Bengal Legislative Counsel adopted the resolution of separating the Judiciary from Executive
- Calcutta students came out of the colleges to protest and demand nationalization of their institution.

1922: - Chauri Chaura incident took place at Gorakhpur district

- Gandhi was arrested for sedition based on the Prevention of Seditious Act 1911

1923: - General Election was held in British India

- Gandhi visited Calcutta and urged the students to boycott government college and take up charkha

1924: - Rastriya Swam Sewak Samiti was founded

- CPI was founded
- Diarchy was suspended in Bengal which was started on the basis of Government of India Act 1919

1926: - Public Service Commission was established which was reconstituted as Federal Public Service Commission by the Government of India Act 1935**1927:** - Simon Commission Formed**1928:** - Simon Commission Landed in India

- Subhas Chandra Bose organized a group of volunteers during the Kolkata session of INC, which was named as Bengal Volunteers Corps
- Students organizing committee was formed in Calcutta, to draft All Bengal Students Association; Under the presidency of Nehru

1929: - All India Congress demands Purna Swaraj in its Lahore Session

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ⁱⁱⁱ 1930: - INC declared January 26th as Independence Day/Purna Swaraj

- To remove the British monopoly on Salt, Dandi march was initiated

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- Province wide Student protest were held with active support of congress leaders
 - Attempts were made by students, to assassinate high government officials
 - Calcutta students started picketing Presidency College, Bethune College and Scottish Church College

1931: - Delhi becomes the capital of India

- Gandhi-Irwin Pact
- Chakra adopted on the flag by INC

1932: - Terrorist attack in Bengal by Master da Suryasen, The Parhartali European Club was torched. The attack was headed by Preetilata Waddader, the alumni of Bethune College

- A student of Diocesan college unsuccessfully shot the Bengal Governor
- All India Student Federation was formed

1934: - CPI was declared as unlawful

- Gandhi suspended the campaign of civil disobedience

1935: - Government of India Act 1935, established the Bengal Legislative assembly and the lower chamber of Bengal Legislature

1936: - INC rejected the new constitution

1937: - Provincial autonomy due to congress winning 26 seats

- 'Students Tribune' journal was started in an attempt to bring all students under one banner
- All India Muslim Students Federation came into existence

1938: - Shimla Accord

1939: - The beginning of World War II

- Formation of New Left Block under Subhash Chandra Bose

1940: - Pakistan Resolution

- Finance bill certified by Viceroy

1941: - Quit India Resolution was passed in the Bombay session of INC

1942: - Quit India Movement

1943: - Bengal Famine

1944: - Bombay Explosion

1946: - Royal Airforce Mutiny

- Royal Indian Navy Mutiny
- Constituent Assembly met for the first time
- 1946-47 planning for partition

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